

Non-parametric confidence intervals for quantiles

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Overview

Existing methods to compute confidence intervals for quantiles are based on parametric assumptions or asymptotic normal approximations. Here we describe a non-parametric method that is free from any assumption (except that the data points form an i.i.d sample). In this method, the interval bounds are data points. Because of this discretization, the actual coverage may be larger than the nominal coverage.

Motivating data

This work was triggered by the analysis of pesticide data briefly presented below.

```
##   Min. 1st Qu.  Median    Mean 3rd Qu.    Max.
## 0.0010 0.0100 0.0160 0.1742 0.0290 10.5000
```

Histogram of x

The distribution is skewed with an outlier. This makes any approach based on the parametric assumptions (e.g. assuming the sample comes from an exponential distribution) questionable. Besides, the sample being $n = 149$, an approach based on the normal approximation of the quantile is not recommended.

Non-parametric approach for one-sided confidence interval

We denote by (X_1, \dots, X_n) the data considered as n independent realizations from the same unknown distribution. For $\alpha \in (0, 1)$ we denote by q_α the number such that $P(X \leq q_\alpha) = \alpha$. We denote the ordered sample by $(X_{(1)}, \dots, X_{(n)})$, i.e. a vector containing the sample values as (X_1, \dots, X_n) but in which entries are sorted in increasing order.

We can see that $X_{(r)} \leq q_\alpha$ if the number of observations $\leq q_\alpha$ is $\geq r$.

Thus $P(X_{(r)} \leq q_\alpha) = P(\#\{obs \leq q_\alpha\} \geq r) = 1 - P(\#\{obs \leq q_\alpha\} < r)$.

Denoting by $F_{n,\alpha}(\cdot)$ the cumulative distribution function of a binomial distribution $B(n, \alpha)$, we have:

$$p(X_{(r)} \leq q_\alpha) = F_{n,\alpha}(r - 1).$$

Now for some probability β , we look for a one-sided confidence interval of the form $] - \infty, X_{(r)}]$ achieving

$$P(q_\alpha \in] - \infty, X_{(r)}]) \geq \beta.$$

$P(q_\alpha \in] - \infty, X_{(r)}]) = P(q_\alpha \leq X_{(r)}) = 1 - P(q_\alpha > X_{(r)}) = 1 - (1 - F_{n,\alpha}(r - 1)) = F_{n,\alpha}(r - 1)$. Therefore, the

sought after upper bound of the confidence interval is the smallest value r achieving $F_{n,\alpha}(r-1) \geq \beta$.

Implementation on pesticide data

Here is a small R function implementing the idea above.

```
ub.leftCI = function(x,alpha,beta)
{
  ## alpha: proba of sought after quantile q_alpha
  ## beta: proba of left sided CI
  ## r: rank of empirical quantile X_(r) achieving P(q_alpha <= X_(r)) > beta
  ## ub: upper bound of one-sided CI
  n = length(x)
  r = min((1:n)[(pbinom(q=(1:n)-1,size=n,p=alpha) >= beta)])
  ub = sort(x)[r]
  return(ub)
}
```

Running it on data we get:

```
ub.leftCI(x,alpha=0.95,beta=0.95)
```

```
## [1] 2.12
```

Exploring this in a more systematic way we get:

α	β	Quantile q_α	Upper bound CI_β
0.95	0.95	0.5698	2.12
0.95	0.99	0.5698	3.2
0.75	0.95	0.029	0.038
0.75	0.99	0.029	0.042
0.5	0.95	0.016	0.018
0.5	0.99	0.016	0.019

Non-parametric approach for two-sided confidence interval

Here is some extra material not used, but stored here for the record.

I derive in a similar way a two-sided CI of the form $[X_{(r)}, X_{(s)}]$.

A two-sided CI is given by the smallest s and the largest r achieving

$$P(q_\alpha < X_{(r)}) \leq (1 - \beta)/2$$

and

$$P(q_\alpha > X_{(s)}) \leq (1 - \beta)/2.$$

The second expression can be re-written as

$$P(q_\alpha \leq X_{(s)}) \geq (1 + \beta)/2.$$

```
## Function returning a two-sided interval
## alpha: proba of sought after quantile q_alpha
## beta: proba of two-sided CI
## r: rank of empirical quantile X_(r) achieving P( X_(r) <= q_alpha <= X_(s) ) > beta
## lb, ub: lower and upper bound CI
IC = function(x,alpha,beta)
{
  n = length(x)
  pbin = pbinom(q=(1:n)-1,size=n,p=alpha)
  ind = (1:n)[( pbin <= (1 - beta)/2)]
  if(length(ind) == 0)
  {lb = -Inf}else
  {
    r = max(ind)
    lb = sort(x)[r]
  }
  ind = (1:n)[(pbin >= (1 + beta)/2)]
  if(length(ind) == 0)
  {ub = Inf}else
  {
    s = min(ind)
    ub = sort(x)[s]
  }
  res = c(lb,ub)
  names(res) = c('lb','ub')
  return(res)
}
```